

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF HEPATOPROTECTORS IN THE COMPLEX TREATMENT OF CHRONIC PANCREATITIS AND TYPE 2 DIABETES

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Background: Currently, the prevalence of diabetes and chronic pancreatitis is the highest among the world's population, especially among the elderly population (≥ 65 years old) compared to other diseases. In addition, the prevalence of these diseases among the population is much younger compared to the age groups, which worries many health workers and government leaders. Many scientists have observed that type 2 diabetes has the highest prevalence of any age group, and this number is projected to increase >4.5 -fold between 2005 and 2050. Among these diseases, the risk of developing acute and chronic diseases such as kidney disease, blindness, stroke, and coronary artery disease is high, causing long-term complications, reduced quality of life, high health care costs, and major public health problems. is releasing. That is why the development of comprehensive treatment and rehabilitation measures for these diseases is one of the main tasks facing the healthcare system.

The purpose of the study: to study the effectiveness of the complex protocol treatment with the addition of a course of the sublingual form of the hepatoprotector to the clinical manifestations of patients with type 2 diabetes and chronic pancreatitis.

Materials and methods: 57 patients with diabetes in remission and chronic pancreatitis were studied. To study the effectiveness of the proposed programs, two groups were formed according to the principles of randomization: group 1 (30 patients) received protocol treatment for one month, group 2 (27 patients) received protocol treatment with a hepatoprotector course.

Results: The effects of two treatment programs on some clinical symptoms and syndromes in patients with chronic pancreatitis were determined. Positive dynamics of clinical symptoms and syndromes were found in both groups of patients. But in group 2, the therapeutic effect was more significant. When analyzing the dynamics of the parameters of the quality of life according to the scale of the specialized gastroenterology survey under the influence of two treatment programs, it was found that the health of patients who received the hepatoprotector for treatment had a positive effect on all indicators ($p < 0.05$). The inclusion of sublingual demetion in the treatment protocol for the treatment of clinical symptoms of chronic pancreatitis and diabetes mellitus 2 has reduced abdominal pain by 8.2%, dyspepsia by 17.8%, constipation by 7.4%, and diarrhea by 7.4%. .9%, proven to increase the effectiveness of correction. A higher total of 13.7%, efficacy of the treatment with the addition of demetion compared to the PL group was found on the parameters of the GSRS questionnaire scale.

Conclusion: The use of sublingual demetion proved to be appropriate in correction of clinical symptoms and complex rehabilitation in patients with chronic pancreatitis and diabetes.